

Relationship between Promotion Mix and Brand Awareness (Case Study: Dizayn)

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia is one of the most developed countries in Southeast Asia, there are many designers from Indonesia who have achieved success at the international level. The Indonesian fashion industry currently contributes 20% to the creative economy sector. In this case, the government also contributes to developing the country's fashion industry in various ways by making policies, providing capital support, and carrying out digital transformation. The development of fashion today is quite rapid, various styles of clothing can change quickly. In addition, the use of technology can be said to be inseparable from human life today. Based on data, technology users in Indonesia continue to grow and are expected to continue to increase until 2025. Various kinds of special brands in Indonesia have sprung up to compete with their respective characteristics. Now there are many consumers who buy clothes with various brand choices online, whether in the marketplace or on social media. Marketplace income in terms of clothing is also experiencing a positive impact from sales of fashion products and in 2020, even during a pandemic, people prefer to buy fashion products over other products. Even in Bandung itself, fashion is a sector that contributes to PAD (Pendapatan Asli Daerah). Bandung is also often used as a benchmark for Indonesian fashion, known as Paris Van Java, which on the other hand also attracts tourists to come to Bandung. One brand that utilizes social media and marketplaces to market and sell its products is Dizayn, which was founded in 2018 in Bandung. In running its business, Dizayn experiences problems in terms of brand awareness from the market, this needs to be studied to increase Dizayn's brand awareness to compete with existing competitors. This study aims to analyze Dizayn's current condition, propose the right promotion mix for Dizayn and propose an implementation plan for the promotional mix solution that has been made. The promotion mix has 5 (five) variables there are of advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, public relations, and direct marketing. The hypotheses of this study are as follows: H1 advertising has a positive relationship with brand awareness, H2 sales promotion has a positive relationship with brand awareness, H3 personal selling has a positive relationship with brand awareness, H4 public relations has a positive relationship with brand awareness, H5 direct marketing has a positive relationship with brand awareness. This study uses multiple linear regression analysis to see the relationship between the independent variable, namely the promotion mix, and the dependent variable, namely brand awareness. The results shows that advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, and direct marketing have a positive relationship with brand awareness, which means that H1, H2, H3 and H5 are acceptable. The promotion mix that has a positive relationship, direct advertising and marketing has the highest significant value, namely 0.000, where this value is less than 0.05. Meanwhile, public relations have a negative relationship, which means that H4 is rejected or unacceptable, which has a significance value of 0.420. The contribution of this research to science is so that in the future this research can be a reference or reference to see the relationship between promotion mix and brand awareness in different industries and larger companies. So that future research continues to develop according to the times. In addition, the results of this research are also expected to be applied by Dizayn so that he can compete fairly in the fashion industry which in the future can increase the contribution of the fashion industry to the creative economy sector and do not rule out the possibility of adding jobs.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Multiple Linear Regression Analysis, Promotion Mix.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the Southeast Asian countries where fashion is thriving. The country values fashion, and many Indonesian designers have achieved international success. Indonesian culture values modesty and elegance, as well as wearing beautiful clothes that are not too flashy or difficult to find [1]. Fashion industry currently contribute 20% to Indonesia creative economy sector.

On the other side, discuss the performance of textile and apparel industry, in the second quarter of 2022 experienced growth per quarter (q on q) of 1.64%. Meanwhile, the annual growth of the textile and apparel industry sector in the first semester of 2022 (year

on year) is 13.10 percent. This growth performance is a significant improvement compared to the performance in 2021 and 2020 which was quite negative [2]. Fashion is not only a primary need but has become an artistic necessity so that it can encourage the growth of this industry more rapidly. According to Yuliana Fitri, Owner, and Designer Aruna Creative.ID said that consumers tend to choose local brands to support national economic recovery. Consumer hope that brand that they choose can socially responsible [3].

Government takes various ways to support the fashion industry, through various steps including credit restructuring stimulus policies, funding support, and digital transformation for MSMEs said Sandiaga Uno [4].

It can't be denied that technological development has grown very fast, can be shown from the data above total internet users is 204.7 million or 73.7% from total Indonesia population, and from 204.7 million user, 191.4 million are active social media users or 68.9% from total Indonesia population. And for cellular mobile connection is 370.1 million or 133.3% from total population, it can be indicated that people can connect from everywhere and anytime. Digital growth in Indonesia is very fast, it can be seen from data above that cellular mobile connection increase 13 million, internet users increase 2.1 million and active social media users increase 21 million from previous year.

Besides, technological developments play a major role in the movement of fashion trends. The development of technology not only moves the trend rotation faster, but also encourages fashion business actors to be more adaptive and creative in creating fashion products that can meet the needs of the community. According to Head of Fashion & Lifestyle Shopee Indonesia, Adi Rahardja said fashion product is one of the categories that most wanted in this marketplace. This also shows that technology makes it easier for people to get fashion products that are used to express themselves through a stylish style [5].

The fashion industry has great potential for brands to continue to innovate following existing trends by approaching them through online media, especially e-commerce. Fashion industry always growing every year, moreover, with the rapid development of technology, it will be easier for brands to see the potential that will become a trend in the future which of course will be a profitable opportunity for the brand if it can follow developments in accordance with existing trends through e-commerce media that can reach wider consumers.

In Bandung, fashion is one of the creative economy sub-sectors that contributed to PAD (Pendapatan Asli Daerah) during the Covid-19 recovery period. This is influenced by the demographics of Bandung, where 68% of the population is under 40 years old. Furthermore, the historical factor as a creative city plays a major role [6]. Since the Covid-19 pandemic, MSME actors have made various efforts to attract buyers through digital marketing, one of which is holding a virtual fashion show that is broadcast live. A virtual fashion show can be used to introduce a brand's latest collection. Virtual fashion shows, according to Irma, can increase people's interest in the products on display [7].

Discuss about women's fashion, Dizayn is one of the brands from Bandung that exist to meet women's fashion needs that already exist since 2018. Dizayn is specialized casual style that usually used for daily use with their unique design and color that easily for customer to mix and match their outfit with Dizayn product.

It can be concluded that there is an opportunity for Dizayn as an online shop to grow because of internet users, social media users, and e-commerce users still increasing. But it can't be denied that there is challenge in tight competition and needs a good brand awareness to be sustained in the market, especially in online fashion industry. Dizayn, as one of the brands that compete using Instagram as its main promotional media realized that they want to deliver the right marketing strategy to increase the sales because of the tight competition in the market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

Marketing is concerned with identifying and satisfying social needs. Meeting needs profitably is one of the best definitions of marketing [8]. The meeting of sellers and buyers to conduct transactions for goods or services is known as marketing [9]. As a result, understanding the market no longer refers to a location but rather to the activities or meetings of sellers and buyers in offering a product to consumers. While marketing is purposeful human activity to meet the needs and desires of customers through a process of exchange and parties with an interest in the company [10]. Marketing is one of the economic activities that contributes to the creation of economic value [11]. The price of goods and services is determined by economic value. Production, marketing, and consumption are all important factors in creating value. Marketing connects production and consumption activities.

Marketing Strategy

Marketing strategy is set of goals and objectives, policies and rules that guide a company's marketing efforts from time to time, at each level, its reference and allocation, particularly as the company's response to the environment and ever-changing competitive conditions [12]. Marketing strategy is choose and analyse the target market, which is a group of people to whom the company wishes to sell its products and develop a marketing mix that is appropriate and capable of satisfying the target market [13]. Creating a marketing strategy need to identify the target market segments and developing a positioning strategy. A strategy for maintaining and strengthening customer relations, as well as a strategy for developing new products, should be developed. Marketing program development needs the definition of product strategy, promotion strategy, marketing strategy, and pricing policy.

Promotion Strategy

Promotion is a set of activities designed to communicate, educate, and persuade people about a product so that they recognize its superiority [14]. By purchasing and wearing it, they will bind their thoughts and feelings to the product in the form of loyalty. Promotion strategy is the art of using and developing power to achieve goals with comprehensive and proper implementation plan that already design by the enterprise to inform, persuade, and remind consumers about the product so that consumer can interested and recognize that the product is better than the competitor.

Promotion Mix

The promotion mix, also known as the marketing communication mix, is a specialized mix of advertising, public relations, personal selling, sales promotion, and direct marketing tools used by businesses to engage consumers, persuasively communicate customer value, and build customer relationships. The promotional mix is a tool in a marketer's toolbox for engaging and communicating with customers and other stakeholders. Each tool must be carefully coordinated with an integrated concept marketing communications (IMC) to convey clear and convincing messages [15].

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness can be measured as a consumer's capacity to recognize a brand under various circumstances [16]. It is associated with the strength of brand nodes or memory trails. This is a step in developing brand equity that is frequently necessary but not always sufficient. Additionally, other factors, like brand image, frequently come into play. Brand awareness is the capacity of consumers to remember and identify a brand under various circumstances and to mentally link brand names, logos, symbols, etc. Building brand awareness is particularly helpful in making sure that customers are aware of the product or service categories in which the brand competes and the goods and services that are offered under that brand name. Brand awareness consists of 2 (two) aspects, brand recall and brand recognition.

Relationship Between Promotion Mix and Brand Awareness

Brand awareness can be effectively increased by increasing advertising spending. Greater advertising reach and brand awareness are frequently results of increasing advertising investment Nikabadi et al. (2015). Advertisements aid in presenting comprehensive information about brand and raise awareness of it [17]. Brands are remembered by consumers because of effective advertising. An advertisement's effectiveness is determined by its execution, message, and brand awareness-raising tactics [18]. Advertising, advertising spending, and consumer's attitudes toward advertisements have positive effect on brand equity and its dimensions Lang et al. (2022).

H1: Advertising has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

Sales promotion defined as activities that frequently occur at a specific location or between groups of customers over time, as well as supplementary benefits provided to induce quick responses Liang et al. (2017). However, due to the financial savings and advantages of sales promotions, customers might be more likely to stick with the product brand Lang et al. (2022). Monetary promotion affects brand awareness but create lower brand image whereas higher brand reputation results from non-monetary actions [17]. As a result, non-monetary promotions tactics can help raise the value of brand [19]. Brand equity is positively impacted by sales promotions, but non-monetary promotions should aim to preserve brand value because, monetary promotions can devalue brands and have a negative impact on their emergence [17].

H2: Sales promotions has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

The three main objectives of personal selling are relationship building and maintenance, action-motivation, and informational selling [20]. Personal selling is a very engaging promotional strategy. A seller and a specific customer or group of customers are in a two-way conversation [21]. Personal selling is a great tool for spreading awareness and creating enduring, reliable relationships with consumers. Because buyers and sellers interact in person, customers learn briefly about goods and services and develop likable and trustworthy relationships with customers, making personal selling a rich source of brand awareness (Kumar & Patra, 2017). Brand awareness is greatly influenced by personal selling [22].

H3: Personal selling has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

An organization's target markets and stakeholders can establish and maintain social relationships with public relations, which facilitates two-way interactions [23]. Consequently, public relations aids businesses in increasing brand recognition and cultivating connections with their intended audience. PR's beneficial effects on aspects of brand equity, including brand awareness Lang et al. (2022). A good company must maintain relationships with its customers and ensure their satisfaction, so it cannot ignore the significance of public relations [17]. Thus, positive brand equity which includes brand awareness and image are created through strong customer relationships. Public relations influence awareness and effectiveness in a positive way [24]. Aspects of brand equity like brand awareness are significantly influenced by public relations [17]. There is a significant relationship between public relations and brand equity [25].

H4: Public relations has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

Offering opportunities for customer-focused marketing and relationship-based direct marketing. Customer-centric marketing refers to goods or services that are strategically in line with consumers' wants and needs, thereby bolstering efforts to build relationships with them [26]. More personal information about our customers is available through direct marketing than through other forms of promotion [17]. Telemarketing, direct mail, and direct mail are all examples of direct marketing techniques. Direct marketing is the process of identifying potential customers and creating brand awareness to boost sales for business. Direct marketing is the most influential dimension that influence brand awareness [25]. Better direct marketing increases consumer brand equity and brand recall [27]. Brand awareness is greatly influenced by direct marketing [22]. Direct marketing also plays an important role in building brand equity [17].

H5: Direct marketing has a positive relationship with brand awareness.

Figure 1 Research Framework
Source: Author, 2023.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses quantitative method because data processed in this study in the form of numbers. Quantitative research is generally carried out on certain population or representative samples [28]. The purpose of this research is descriptive. Descriptive research was carried out to provide a more detailed overview of a symptom or phenomenon [29]. Because data collection is done only once, the time spent conducting the research is included in the cross sectional. Cross-sectional research is research that is conducted at one time. The measurement scale used in this study is the ordinal scale with the type of scale used is Likert scale. Ordinal scales not only categorize variables in such a way as to show differences among the various categories, but also sort order of categories in some meaningful way [30]. Collecting quantitative research data is an effort by researchers to collect numerical or non-numerical data that can be quantified [31]. When viewed from the data source, then data collection can use primary and secondary sources [28].

This research using a questionnaire tool distributed via online media to the pre-determined respondents, people who interested in purchases fashion online. Questionnaire is data collection techniques in which respondents are asked to answer a series of questions or written statements [28]. Secondary data is sources that do not directly provide data to data collectors, such as other people or documents. In this research secondary data is collected from news, book, website, previous research, and other media to support the theoretical in this research. The population on this research is people who are interested in purchases fashion online that will drive to increasing brand awareness. Sampling technique in this study is non-probability because non-probability sampling is purposive sampling subjective [31]. Non-probability sampling does not provide opportunities for each population unit to be selected as a sample unit. While the type of non-probability sampling in this study is purposive sampling or deliberate sampling. Because the purpose of this research is to find out what kind of promotion mix strategy that is suitable to Dizayn consumers. Then the sample set is potential consumers of Dizayn. In this research the author chooses respondents male or female with aged more than 17 years old who interested in purchases fashion online which amounted to 200 samples refer to Nunen, et al. (2020) because this research is to find suitable promotion mix strategy that can increase awareness of Dizayn so, it included to problem-solving research.

Validity Test

Validity assessment of the chosen instrument, determining whether it is accurate enough to measure what needs to be measured or not. There are several steps involved in determining whether the instrument is present, including comparing the calculated values with table values. The item is deemed valid if r count is greater than or equal to r table. However, the item is deemed invalid if r count < r table [31]. Comparison of the r count values (correlation) with r table is the test criterion (product moment table) where n (number of samples) is 200. Using a 5% (0.05) level of significance, the value of the r table was calculated to be 0.138 [28].

Table 1 Validity Test

Validity Test				
Variable	r count	r table	Significance	Description
AD_1	0.421	0.138	0,000	Valid
AD_2	0.740	0.138	0,000	Valid
AD_3	0.778	0.138	0,000	Valid
AD_4	0.823	0.138	0,000	Valid
AD_5	0.837	0.138	0,000	Valid
AD_6	0.818	0.138	0,000	Valid
SP_1	0.579	0.138	0,000	Valid
SP_2	0.824	0.138	0,000	Valid
SP_3	0.876	0.138	0,000	Valid
SP_4	0.829	0.138	0,000	Valid
SP_5	0.785	0.138	0,000	Valid
PS_1	0.684	0.138	0,000	Valid
PS_2	0.774	0.138	0,000	Valid
PS_3	0.844	0.138	0,000	Valid
PS_4	0.764	0.138	0,000	Valid
PS_5	0.729	0.138	0,000	Valid
PR_1	0.721	0.138	0,000	Valid
PR_2	0.695	0.138	0,000	Valid
PR_3	0.784	0.138	0,000	Valid
PR_4	0.844	0.138	0,000	Valid
PR_5	0.833	0.138	0,000	Valid
DM_1	0.641	0.138	0,000	Valid
DM_2	0.728	0.138	0,000	Valid

DM_3	0.826	0.138	0,000	Valid
DM_4	0.831	0.138	0,000	Valid
BA_1	0.887	0.138	0,000	Valid
BA_2	0.890	0.138	0,000	Valid
BA_3	0.912	0.138	0,000	Valid
BA_4	0.861	0.138	0,000	Valid
BA_5	0.889	0.138	0,000	Valid

Source: Author, 2023

Reliability Test

Instrument reliability is assessed using a reliability test [31]. If a measurement yields predictable results, it is said to be reliable. Coefficient of variation if the value is above 0.7 is acceptable, while if the value is above 0.8 then the reliability is good.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Reliability Test			
Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	α	Description
Advertising	0.834	0.7	Reliable
Sales Promotion	0.839	0.7	Reliable
Personal Selling	0.816	0.7	Reliable
Public Relation	0.835	0.7	Reliable
Direct Marketing	0.752	0.7	Reliable
Brand Awareness	0.933	0.7	Reliable

Source: Author, 2023

Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-4.121	.861		-4.785	.000		
	Advertising	.318	.078	.313	4.072	.000	.264	3.795
	SalesPromotion	.205	.087	.178	2.366	.019	.274	3.653
	PersonalSelling	.206	.083	.174	2.467	.014	.314	3.188
	PublicRelation	-.061	.075	-.052	-.809	.420	.378	2.649
	DirectMarketing	.464	.105	.310	4.436	.000	.319	3.130

a. Dependent Variable: BrandAwareness

Figure 2. Multicollinearity Test

Source: Author, 2023

- **Criteria:**
If the Tolerance value is > 0.100 and the VIF value is < 10.00 then there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.
- **Data Analysis:**
On this research, the independent variable consisting of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing has a Tolerance value > 0.100 and a VIF value < 10.00, so this study does not experience symptoms of multicollinearity or in other words the multicollinearity test is fulfilled.

Normality Test (P-P Plot & Kolmogorov-Smirnov)

Figure 3 P-P Plot
Source: Author, 2023.

- Data Analysis:
The distribution of data spreads and follows a straight line diagonally so in this study the data is normally distributed.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		200
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.33423994
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.074
	Positive	.051
	Negative	-.074
Test Statistic		.074
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.009 ^c
Exact Sig. (2-tailed)		.211
Point Probability		.000

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Figure 4. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test
Source: Author, 2023.

- Criteria:
If the exact sig (2-tailed) value is greater than 0.05, it means that the data is normally distributed.
- Data Analysis:
The exact sig (2-tailed) value obtained is 0.211 which was greater than 0.05, meaning that the data in this study were normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity Test (Scatterplot & Glesjer)

Figure 5. Scatterplot
Source: Author, 2023.

• Data Analysis:

Based on the scatterplot figure above, there is no clear pattern and the distribution of the data spreads above and below or around the number of 0, which means that this research does not have heteroscedasticity symptoms, or the assumptions of the heteroscedasticity test are fulfilled.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.072	.496		6.193	.000
	Advertising	-.080	.045	-.240	-1.783	.076
	SalesPromotion	-.065	.050	-.173	-1.310	.192
	PersonalSelling	.064	.048	.165	1.339	.182
	PublicRelation	.016	.043	.043	.378	.706
	DirectMarketing	-.003	.060	-.005	-.042	.967

a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES

Figure 6. Glesjer
Source: Author, 2023.

• Criteria:

If the significance value is > 0.05, it means that the data does not show heteroscedasticity, and vice versa.

• Data Analysis:

- Advertising variable has a significance value of 0.076 which is greater than 0.05.
- Sales Promotion variable has a significance value of 0.192 which is greater than 0.05.
- Personal Selling variable has a significance value of 0.182 which is greater than 0.05.

- Public Relations variable has a significance value of 0.706 which is greater than 0.05.
- Direct Marketing variable has a significance value of 0.967 which is greater than 0.05.
- Conclusion:
All independent variables consisting of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing have a significance value greater than 0.05, which means that in this study there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity, or the assumptions of the heteroscedasticity test have been fulfilled.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

F Test

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2505.347	5	501.069	89.651	.000 ^b
	Residual	1084.287	194	5.589		
	Total	3589.634	199			

a. Dependent Variable: BrandAwareness

b. Predictors: (Constant), DirectMarketing, Advertising, PublicRelation, PersonalSelling, SalesPromotion

Figure 7. ANOVA

Source: Author, 2023.

- Criteria:
If the significance value is < 0.05, it means that independent variables have a significant relationship simultaneously (together) with the dependent variable.
- Data Analysis:
The significance value of the F test results obtained a significance value of 0.000 where the result was < 0.005 and this means that all independent variables consisting of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing have a significant relationship simultaneously (together) with the dependent variable is Brand Awareness.

Partial Test or Hypothesis Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-4.121	.861		-4.785	.000
	Advertising	.318	.078	.313	4.072	.000
	SalesPromotion	.205	.087	.178	2.366	.019
	PersonalSelling	.206	.083	.174	2.467	.014
	PublicRelation	-.061	.075	-.052	-.809	.420
	DirectMarketing	.464	.105	.310	4.436	.000

a. Dependent Variable: BrandAwareness

Figure 8. Coefficients

Source: Author, 2023.

- Criteria:
If the significance value is < 0.05, it means that independent variables have a significant relationship with the dependent variable.
- Data Analysis:
➤ Advertising variable has a significance value of 0.000 which is lower than 0.05, it means that Advertising variable have a significant relationship with Brand Awareness, so H1 is accepted.

- Sales Promotion variable has a significance value of 0.019 which is lower than 0.05, it means that Sales Promotion variable have a significant relationship with Brand Awareness, so H2 is accepted.
 - Personal Selling variable has a significance value of 0.014 which is lower than 0.05, it means that Personal Selling variable have a significant relationship with Brand Awareness, so H3 is accepted.
 - Public Relations variable has a significance value of 0.420 which is greater than 0.05, it means that Public Relations variable have no relationship with Brand Awareness, so H4 is rejected.
 - Direct Marketing variable has a significance value of 0.000 which is lower than 0.05, it means that Direct Marketing variable have a significant relationship with Brand Awareness, so H5 is accepted.
- Multiple Linear Regression Equation:

$$BA = (-4.121) + 0.318AD + 0.205SP + 0.206PS + (-0.061)PR + 0.464DM$$
 - Regression Equation Analysis:
 - The constant value obtained is -4,121, which means that if in this study all independent variables are considered 0 (zero) or in other words there is no Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing then Brand Awareness will negative of -4,121. Negative constant values can be interpreted as 0 (zero) so, that in this study it is stated that if there are no independent variables consisting of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing then Brand Awareness will not happen.
 - Value of Regression Coefficient of the Advertising Variable has a positive value of 0.318, meaning that if there is a 1% increase in the Advertising variable, it will cause an increase in Brand Awareness of 0.318.
 - Value of Regression Coefficient of the Sales Promotion Variable has a positive value of 0.205, meaning that if there is a 1% increase in the Sales Promotion variable, it will cause an increase in Brand Awareness of 0.205.
 - Value of Regression Coefficient of the Personal Selling Variable has a positive value of 0.206, meaning that if there is a 1% increase in the Personal Selling variable, it will cause an increase in Brand Awareness of 0.206.
 - Value of the Regression Coefficient of the Public Relations Variable has a negative value of -0.061, meaning that if there is a 1% increase in the Public Relations variable, it will cause a decrease in Brand Awareness of 0.061.
 - Value of Regression Coefficient of the Direct Marketing Variable has a positive value of 0.464, meaning that if there is a 1% increase in the Direct Marketing variable, it will cause an increase in Brand Awareness of 0.464.

Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.835 ^a	.698	.690	2.364129

a. Predictors: (Constant), DirectMarketing, Advertising, PublicRelation, PersonalSelling, SalesPromotion

Figure 9. Model Summary

Source: Author, 2023.

- Data Analysis:
 Based on the model summary table above, it is found that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.690, which means that the independent variables consisting of Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing contribute 69% to the dependent variable, namely Brand Awareness and the rest, which is equal to 31% or 0.310, is a relationship from other variables outside this research.

BUSINESS SOLUTION

Advertising to Increase Brand Awareness

Dizayn can also take advantage of celebrity programs and artists who can describe Dizayn products as in the personas previously described. The selection of celebrities or artists that suit Dizayn's characteristics is very important because it will affect what Dizayn wants to convey, what Dizayn products are like, and who the Dizayn products are for. It takes more than a single or even two instances of advertising exposure to get consumers to remember and believe in a brand.

Sales Promotion to Increase Brand Awareness

For Dizayn itself to build brand awareness it is better to do sales promotion as often as possible combining non-monetary and monetary promotions. For non-monetary Dizayn can give such as gold, brand merchandise, discount for next purchase, mystery box, giveaway or even free product or buy 1 get 1. Non-monetary promotion can be used by Dizayn during a time when sales are low to boost awareness and to build brand recognition. For monetary promotion Dizayn can give such as price-off, rebates, coupon. Monetary promotion can be used by Dizayn during a time when sales are high such as national day, Christmas, Eid, New Years, and another celebrating day because according to Fransiska et al. (2012) these days usually revenue increase twice or more to boost awareness because Dizayn compete in highly competitive market so there are many competitors it is important for Dizayn to make something different and something brave to build brand recall.

Personal Selling to Increase Brand Awareness

For Dizayn itself it can be use salesperson with understanding and knowledge as well as good communication skills to be able to reach potential consumers which can be done online or offline when participating in fashion exhibitions Fransiska et al. (2012) so that the message of the product can be conveyed properly to consumers so that brand recognition will arise from the minds of consumers which can encourage improvement of sales from Dizayn. Presentation or demonstration can be done by utilize social media live in certain period time, Dizayn should make a schedule for its salesperson to do live on social media such Instagram, but I suggest Dizayn to expand into another social media such as TikTok to do live because TikTok is more happening today especially to sell product, there are so many brand today utilize TikTok to sell their product especially if doing live, it can be reach more potential consumer for Dizayn because TikTok can reach people who are not followers easily with the FYP feature it has.

Direct Marketing to Increase Brand Awareness

In general, direct marketing associates are beneficial for raising brand awareness because brands are already focusing on audiences who have expressed interest in the brand or its sector. Direct marketing may annoy some consumers, but if it is segmented correctly and presented creatively in your campaigns, it may very well be the most successful tactic for establishing relationships with your current customers and introducing your brand to potential customers. The direct marketing type that can adopt by Dizayn is email marketing and door to door. So, by doing this, Dizayn also gets several benefits, including building connections with potential customers, making an emotional approach, and being able to interact directly with the products offered.

Referring to the finding of this research, it found that advertising and direct marketing have the biggest relationship with brand awareness. Therefore, Dizayn should focus on maximizing the advertising and direct marketing first before diving into personal selling and the last is sales promotion. So, based on this research result advertising and direct marketing must be the priority for Dizayn to run the promotion in the future.

CONCLUSION

There are some strategies to overcome the issues faced by Dizayn. First, make an advertising using steps that can make people interest with Dizayn brand and endorsement with appropriate artist/celebrity that represent Dizayn character. Second, doing sales promotions in monetary and non-monetary way. Third, utilize social media live and try expanding to another social media such as TikTok to reach more people and of course equip the salesperson with brand knowledge, communication skills, and the ability to interact with potential customers within the brand. Dizayn should have a reward system in place for their top-performing sales teams. And the last is direct marketing using email marketing and door to door in e-commerce or social media WhatsApp to directly bring the product or offer to potential consumer. All the strategies also need to consider national or big day to get more intention from potential consumer.

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